

Low complexity neural network equalizer for nonlinearity mitigation in digital subcarrier multiplexing systems

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Abstract: This article conducts a comparative study of the complexity reduction of neural network (NN) models for nonlinearity compensation used in digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM)-based optical communication systems. We employ the NN model based on bi-directional long short-term memory (biLSTM) and 1D-convolutional NN (1D-CNN) layers. To reduce the computation complexity of the proposed solution, weight clustering is applied to the NN. We specifically compare the performance of our proposed NN-based equalizer with traditional methods such as Chromatic Dispersion Compensation (CDC), Digital Back-Propagation (DBP) and alternative NN, based on triplet coefficients in perturbation analysis, proposed in previous literature, evaluating both Q-factor performance and computational complexity. Our findings show that the NN-based equalizer offers competitive Q-factor improvements while significantly reducing computational complexity, particularly when weight clustering is used. We show that the complexity of the NN can be reduced by up to 91.1% compared to the NN based on the perturbation analysis proposed in previous literature and by 31.5% compared to the DBP with 1 step per span. The results underscore the potential of NN-based approaches to deliver high-performance nonlinear compensation with lower computational demands, positioning them as a promising solution for future optical nonlinear equalizers.

1. Introduction

In high-speed optical communications, mitigating fiber nonlinearity is essential to achieve higher transmission rates and improved signal quality. Fiber nonlinearity (e.g., the Kerr effect) imposes significant limitations on the optical launch power, consequently constraining the information rate in modern coherent transmission systems. The importance of optical nonlinearity increases as the transmission bandwidth continues to expand [1, 2]. To mitigate the impact of such nonlinearity, various digital signal processing (DSP) techniques have been proposed [3]. These methods include digital back-propagation (DBP) [4, 5], perturbation-based nonlinearity compensation (NLC) approaches [6], and Volterra series-based equalizers [7]. However, a common challenge with these techniques is their high computational complexity, which limits their practical application in real-time systems.

Over the past two decades, significant progress has been made in the use of machine learning, specifically neural networks (NN), within digital communication [8]. Due to their universal approximation capability, NNs have emerged as promising tools for optical channel post-equalization. This ability enables them to accurately approximate the inverse optical channel transfer function and mitigate nonlinear distortions. Although NN-based solutions can offer lower computational complexity than traditional mitigation techniques [9], the main challenges

46 that still hinder their practical implementation are (i) achieving high-speed processing and (ii)
47 managing computational complexity. Among the various NN architectures, recurrent NNs
48 (RNNs), such as long short-term memory (LSTM) modules have shown better equalization
49 performance compared to feed-forward NNs when addressing nonlinear impairments [10, 11],
50 since the LSTM layer is suitable for time-series processes. Several authors have investigated
51 LSTM- or NN-based equalizers in single-carrier transmission systems [10–12], however, a
52 limited number of works [13, 14] investigated the NN-based equalizer in the digital subcarrier
53 multiplexing (DSCM) system. DSCM has recently emerged as an effective alternative to cope
54 with the current rapid evolution of internet traffic, e.g. to limit effects such as equalization-
55 enhanced phase noise (EEPN) [15]. It has also been proven to provide more robustness against
56 nonlinearity distortion by optimizing symbol rates compared to single-carrier systems [16, 17].
57 DSCM and Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) differ in how subcarriers are
58 managed. While OFDM relies on overlapping subcarriers with carefully maintained orthogonality
59 for efficient spectrum utilization, DSCM uses fully separated subcarriers with virtually zero
60 frequency cross-talk, simplifying receiver design. Compared to OFDM, DSCM offers greater
61 resilience to time-frequency synchronization challenges within DSP algorithms. This advantage
62 arises because OFDM operates at a much lower symbol rate, which complicates the detection of
63 subcarriers, particularly when signals originate from multiple OFDM transmitters at varying
64 distances [18]. Finally, its use provides significant flexibility, resulting in reduced capital and
65 operational expenditures in optical networks [19, 20].

66 Bakhshali et al. [13] have already proposed NN architectures for optical channel nonlinear
67 compensation in DSCM systems. However, the complexity of their approach remains considerable.
68 Therefore, further complexity reductions are paramount in the path toward real implementation
69 and sustainable nonlinear equalizers.

70 This work investigates nonlinear compensation in DSCM transmission systems by applying the
71 NN-based post-equalizer. In addition, the model compression technique “weight clustering” is
72 applied. Weight clustering reduces the number of effective weights used by the model, resulting
73 in a significant decrease in computational complexity [21]. The contribution of this article can
74 be summarized as follows:

- 75 • We demonstrate how the input structure and the NN architecture are adapted to simultane-
76 ously recover signals from all subcarriers in DSCM systems.
- 77 • We investigated the potential of weight clustering as a complexity reduction technique in
78 an NN-based equalizer used in DSCM systems.
- 79 • We propose the low-complexity NN model that offers a reduction of up to 34% in
80 computational complexity in terms of real multiplications per equalized symbols (RMpS),
81 compared to the standard DBP 1 STpS (step per span) and up to 97.9% RMpS reduction
82 compared to its uncompressed version.
- 83 • We propose NN models leading to optical performance similar to that reported in [13], but
84 with a reduction of up to 91% complexity in RMpS.
- 85 • We compare the trade-off between the NN models’ performance and complexity with
86 different numbers of weight clusters (WC).

87 This article is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the NN-based equalizer and the
88 NN architecture adopted in this work. Section 3 presents the model compression technique,
89 weight clustering, which is the main approach used in this study. Section 4 describes the DSCM
90 simulator used to generate the data to train the NN, how the NNs were trained, and the benchmark
91 used in this model. Section 5 discusses the computational complexity of different approaches for

Fig. 1. The NN equalizer design employs biLSTM and 1D-CNN layers, utilizing the data from all four SCs as inputs to simultaneously recover symbols in the x-polarization across all four SCs.

92 NLC, namely the original NN structures, the weight-clustered NNs, and the analytical approaches
 93 like DBP. Lastly, Section 6 discusses the findings of this work compared to the previous literature.

94 2. NN-based equalizers

95 Due to their universal approximation ability, the NNs have been widely studied and investigated
 96 as promising tools for optical channel post-equalization. NNs have been shown to outperform
 97 the DBP approach in terms of computational complexity [21]. However, the complexity of
 98 NN is still a major issue of the real implementation. In this paper, we address the reduction of
 99 complexity in the NN-based equalizer (see Section 3). The utilization of NN in DSCM is notably
 100 under-researched. Various architectures of NN have been proposed for nonlinear mitigation
 101 in single-channel, single-carrier transmission systems, such as multi-layer perception (MLP),
 102 convolutional NN, or RNNs. However, feedforward NNs like MLP and CNN have demonstrated
 103 inferior performance compared to RNN- or biLSTM-based architectures [10]. Due to the
 104 increased complexity in DSCM systems arising from the nonlinearities of adjacent subcarriers,
 105 the constraints of MLPs and CNNs are expected to be even more significant. Consequently, the
 106 NN architecture proposed here is a combination of the biLSTM and CNN model, as depicted in
 107 Fig. 1. The architecture based on an LSTM layer has shown superior performance in previous
 108 research works [11, 13, 21]. Unlike RNNs that face short-term memory limitations, LSTM
 109 networks are capable of learning long-term dependencies across time steps, which are essential
 110 to mitigate dispersion-induced memory effects and intersymbol interference (ISI) caused by
 111 chromatic dispersion [11]. LSTM was specifically designed to overcome the gradient challenges
 112 associated with RNNs [22, 23]. The core properties of the LSTM-based layer are sequential
 113 processing and retaining past information through past hidden states. The biLSTM layer adopted
 114 here consists of two separate LSTM layers for forward and backward directions. The equations
 115 of the LSTM layer and its complexity can be found in Section 5.1. Note that all of our NN-based
 116 equalizers in this work operate at one sample per symbol.

117 In this work, the biLSTM layer has 111 hidden units (n_h), and the 1D-CNN layer adopts 8
 118 filters (n_f) and a kernel size (n_k) of 15 with the linear activation function. This 1D-CNN layer
 119 has 8 filters to recover the real and imaginary parts of the X polarization of all four subcarriers
 120 simultaneously. Note that while it is possible to modify the NN output to recover both X and Y
 121 polarizations simultaneously, this was not tested in this study. For consistency, the Chromatic
 122 Dispersion Compensation (CDC) block and the NN equalizer were applied separately to each

123 polarization. The input window (M) has a size of 221 input symbols. In order to equalize the
124 signal in DSCM systems, the NN takes in 16 input features that consist of real and imaginary parts
125 of X and Y polarization for four subcarriers. In this way, the NN can have sufficient knowledge to
126 learn the pattern of nonlinear distortions like self-subcarrier nonlinearity (SSN), including those
127 arising from the neighboring subcarriers, and mitigate the cross-subcarrier nonlinearity (CSN).
128 The model performs a regression task to predict the real and imaginary parts of the recovered
129 symbols, or 207 symbols for each subcarrier per one inference step. To recover multiple symbols,
130 it is necessary to account for the system memory length induced by chromatic dispersion in fiber
131 communication systems. When the NN equalizer processes a window of M input symbols, only
132 $M - x$ symbols can be reliably recovered, where x depends on the system's memory length. This
133 is because the initial and final symbols in the input window lack sufficient information from
134 their neighboring symbols (due to dispersion-induced memory effects), making them difficult to
135 recover accurately. To address this, the dimensionality of the input window is reduced without
136 losing crucial information by using a 1D convolutional layer. This layer processes the data with a
137 kernel size n_k , zero padding, dilation, and stride set to 1. As a result, the size of the recovery
138 window becomes $M - n_k + 1$. The loss function used in this model is MSE, and the optimizer is
139 Adam with a learning rate of $5.81 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

140 We included results with 214 hidden units for biLSTM, which yielded marginally better
141 performance, aligning with findings in [13] for comparison. Bayesian Optimizer [10] was utilized
142 to optimize the NN hyperparameters. The optimized hyperparameters included the learning rate,
143 batch size, number of hidden units in the biLSTM layer, and number of output window taps. We
144 defined a range of acceptable values for each hyperparameter optimized to ensure that we did not
145 end up with very high complexity. For example, models with 214 hidden units were selected to
146 achieve the highest Q factor, while models with 111 hidden units were chosen to demonstrate a
147 reasonable trade-off between complexity and performance. Models with fewer hidden units were
148 not included in our study, as our primary goal was to maintain a performance level comparable to
149 existing benchmarks while optimizing computational efficiency.

150 3. Complexity reduction of NN using weight clustering

151 The weight clustering method illustrated in Fig. 2, which is also known as weight-sharing, is a
152 model compression technique that reduces the computational complexity of NN by decreasing
153 the number of distinct weight values used in the model. This method takes advantage of the
154 observation that many connections in an NN can share the same weight value [24, 25] and, as a
155 result, significantly reduce the number of unique multipliers needed during matrix multiplication.
156 The shared weights can be defined by the centroids' initialization technique, thus ensuring that
157 multiple weights will converge to the nearest centroid. In addition, one can fine-tune those
158 shared weights to improve accuracy. In this work, we carried out a two-step training method.
159 The original model without weight clustering was first trained to achieve good performance
160 and well-trained weights; after that, the weights after clustering were fine-tuned to mitigate the
161 approximation errors. The number of multiplications required in the NN is reduced by applying
162 weight clustering, as multiple operations can be combined into a single multiplication followed
163 by additions. The number of distinct multipliers in matrix multiplication is reduced to at least the
164 number of clusters per input element. For example, the weight matrix on the top left in Fig. 2 is
165 the matrix W . To define the output vector O before clustering, we need to multiply the input
166 vector I by the matrix W . In this example, multiplying W and I leads to 16 real multiplications
167 (input size \times hidden layer size = 4×4), as follows:

Fig. 2. Illustration of weight clustering framework where the trained weights of the original MLP model (top) are clustered into 3 weight clusters with the closest centroid.

$$O = W \times I = \begin{bmatrix} w_{11} & w_{12} & w_{13} & w_{14} \\ w_{21} & w_{22} & w_{23} & w_{24} \\ w_{31} & w_{32} & w_{33} & w_{34} \\ w_{41} & w_{42} & w_{43} & w_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_1 \\ i_2 \\ i_3 \\ i_4 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

168 To cluster the weights into three clusters, as an example in Fig. 2 (bottom left), the centroids of 3
 169 clusters are calculated as c_1 , c_2 , and c_3 . This can be seen as:

$$O = \begin{bmatrix} o_1 \\ o_2 \\ o_3 \\ o_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_2 & c_3 & c_1 & c_2 \\ c_2 & c_3 & c_2 & c_3 \\ c_2 & c_3 & c_2 & c_3 \\ c_2 & c_2 & c_1 & c_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_1 \\ i_2 \\ i_3 \\ i_4 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

170 In this case, the multiplications can be rearranged by summing first the input elements that share
 171 the common weight clusters. The number of multiplications is reduced to 9 multiplications from

172 the original 16 multiplications as follows:

$$O = \begin{bmatrix} o_1 \\ o_2 \\ o_3 \\ o_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (i_1 + i_4)c_2 + i_2c_3 + i_3c_1 \\ (i_1 + i_3)c_2 + (i_2 + i_4)c_3 \\ (i_1 + i_3)c_2 + (i_2 + i_4)c_3 \\ (i_1 + i_2 + i_4)c_2 + i_3c_1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

173 In the worst case, the number of multiplications would be 12 real multiplications (input size \times
 174 the number of clusters = 4×3), as it carries out all possible unique multiplications and the rest
 175 are only additions. The benefits of weight clustering depend on the size of the input vectors, the
 176 weight matrices, and how the trained weight pattern spreads over the weight matrix.

177 After the weights are clustered, the fine-tuning process can be applied to mitigate the impact
 178 of clustering on the optical performance. In this work, we apply a clustering algorithm [25]
 179 from the TensorFlow framework. During training, the gradients are computed with respect to
 180 these centroids, allowing the network to optimize while minimizing the number of unique weight
 181 values. This is accomplished through a lookup table that maps weights to centroids during the
 182 forward pass and updates the centroids during backpropagation. This approach effectively reduces
 183 the number of distinct multipliers in matrix operations, resulting in significantly lower overall
 184 computational load. Additionally, weight clustering acts as a form of non-uniform quantization,
 185 where the NN's weight distribution is optimized to fit a limited set of values. This not only
 186 simplifies the hardware implementation and enables better memory efficiency, but also maintains
 187 the model's optical performance close to its original uncompressed state.

188 It is worth noting that the fine-tuning or training phase for weight-clustered models indeed
 189 involves additional computational cost due to an additional stage to fine-tune the clustered weights.
 190 However, this fine-tuning typically requires only about 10 to 20% of the original training epochs
 191 in this study. In this work, the main focus is on the complexity of inference, specifically in terms
 192 of real multiplications, as this metric directly reflects the cost of implementing the model in
 193 real-world deployments. It is common practice to train the model on a more powerful device
 194 and deploy it on a resource-constrained one. While training complexity can be assessed using
 195 metrics such as the number of trainable parameters, training epochs, or total training time [9],
 196 this analysis falls outside the scope of this study.

197 4. Data generation, NN training and benchmarking models

198 4.1. Data generation using the DSCM simulator

199 The numerical simulator created the dataset assuming a single-channel DSCM transmission
 200 with 4 subcarriers and 16-QAM dual-polarization modulation format. The total symbol rate
 201 is 32 GBd, resulting in 8 GBd per subcarrier. The transmission length is 40×80 km along
 202 standard single-mode fiber (SSMF) spans. The SSMF is modeled with an effective area of $80 \mu m^2$,
 203 chromatic dispersion coefficient $D = 17$ ps/(nm·km), and attenuation parameter $\alpha = 0.2$ dB/km.
 204 The block diagram of the system is reported in Fig. 3. Furthermore, we have also considered
 205 transmission along TrueWave Classic (TWC) fiber with a total fiber length of 15×80 km and
 206 with the fiber parameters $\gamma = 2.5$ (W·km) $^{-1}$, $D = 2.8$ ps/(nm·km), and $\alpha = 0.23$ dB/km.

207 We assume ideal electrical components, a Mach-Zhender modulator, a digital-to-analog
 208 converter (DAC), and an analog-to-digital converter (ADC) along with ideal TX/RX laser sources
 209 having zero linewidths and an ideal optical front end at the receiver. Moreover, electronic noise
 210 sources are not considered for the simplicity of our analysis. Note that, in modern coherent
 211 transceivers, nonlinearities from devices such as the Mach-Zehnder modulator are typically
 212 mitigated (i) using a digital pre-distortion module included within the DSP at the transceiver,

Fig. 3. Considered simulation setup.

213 or (ii) by operating the Mach-Zehnder in a linear regime. The primary focus of this work is to
 214 demonstrate a proof-of-concept method for mitigating fiber-induced nonlinearities; therefore, the
 215 electrical components are assumed to be ideal, and their nonlinear effects are out of the scope of
 216 this work.

217 At the transmitter side, the digital signals of each subcarrier are filtered by a digital root-raised
 218 cosine (RRC) filter with a 1/16 roll-off, shifted to different frequencies, and multiplexed in the
 219 frequency domain. Subsequently, the pre-CDC was performed, where 50% of the total dispersion
 220 is digitally pre-compensated. The full-band signal is finally inverse Fourier transformed to the
 221 time domain and propagated. The propagation of the signal through the fiber was modeled
 222 according to the well-known Manakov equation [26]. The simulations were carried out based
 223 on a full-band symmetric split-step method [27] with an adaptive step size [28]. At the end of
 224 each fiber span, optical fiber losses are perfectly compensated for by an Erbium-Doped Fiber
 225 Amplifier (EDFA) with a 6 dB noise figure.

226 On the receiver side, all subcarriers are captured simultaneously in a single detection. The
 227 subcarrier multiplexed signal is digitized by an ideal ADC and re-sampled to twice the total
 228 symbol rate. Note that oversampling at three or more samples per symbol can have a slight
 229 improvement in the DBP algorithm but is not considered in this work (see [29]). After the
 230 transform to the frequency domain, each subcarrier is successively shifted to the baseband and
 231 filtered out using a digital matched RRC filter. Finally, the low-symbol-rate signal in each
 232 subcarrier is down-sampled at 2 samples per symbol. Standard DSP algorithms [30] are used for
 233 the post-processing of the received signals from each subcarrier, independently. Digital chromatic
 234 dispersion compensation is considered at the front end of the DSP unit for the post-compensation
 235 of 50% of the total link dispersion when only linear equalization is considered; that is, NLC
 236 is not performed. For the case of the 16-QAM format, we use a training symbol-assisted
 237 decision-directed least mean square (DD-LMS) with 1024 training symbols and a 21-tap filter to
 238 implement the multiple input multiple output (MIMO) equalization [30]. A feedforward carrier
 239 recovery (CR) based on maximum likelihood estimation [31] is adopted for phase correction
 240 under correlated nonlinear phase noise. Within the CR algorithm, a joint CR method [32] has
 241 been chosen for cycle slip corrections under non-differential phase coding. Afterward, the bit
 242 error rate (BER) analysis is performed based on the statistical Monte Carlo method. Finally, the
 243 received symbols are used as inputs for the NN. The NN operates at one sample per symbol.

244 Note that the channel parameters are set to match the parameters of the simulator in [13].
 245 For SSMF 40×80 km, our simulator matched the optimum power and Q-factor of [13]. The
 246 performance in the nonlinear regime of our simulator and the simulator in [13] is almost
 247 indistinguishable, while in the linear regime, our simulator provided a slightly better Q-factor
 248 than the simulator in [13]. However, our main focus remains the nonlinear regime.

249 **4.2. NN training**

250 The training datasets were generated with a random bitstream consisting of 2^{19} symbols. For
 251 each epoch, a subset of 2^{18} symbols was randomly selected from this dataset as input symbols
 252 to train the model. For testing and validation, the dataset contained 2^{17} unseen symbols. All
 253 models in this work were trained, validated and tested with the same dataset size. The training
 254 was carried out for 1000 epochs and a mini-batch size of 3824. The mini-batch input of the NN
 255 was structured in three dimensions [10]: $(B, n_s, 16)$ where B is the mini-batch size and n_s is the
 256 number of time steps or the memory size depending on the number of neighbor symbols N as
 257 $n_s = 2N + 1$. The last dimension, 16, corresponds to the number of features for each symbol
 258 across all four subcarriers. The models used four input features per subcarrier, derived from
 259 the in-phase and quadrature components of the complex signal ($X_I, X_Q, Y_I,$ and Y_Q), where
 260 $X_I + jX_Q$ and $Y_I + jY_Q$ are the signals in the X and Y polarizations, respectively. The NN output
 261 is designed to recover the real and imaginary parts of multiple symbols across all four subcarriers
 262 in the X polarization simultaneously. The output batch shape is defined as $(B, n_s - n_k + 1, 8)$,
 263 where $n_s - n_k + 1$ is the number of symbols recovered in the output and the third dimension is 8
 264 as it refers to the real and imaginary parts of the X polarization of four subcarriers.

265 The weights of the trained models were saved at the epoch where the BER on the test dataset
 266 was at its minimum, a technique known as early stopping. Once the model was trained for a
 267 specific launch power, transfer learning [33] was employed to transfer the learned knowledge to
 268 different launch powers, thereby accelerating the training process for these new conditions.

269 Once we had the uncompressed trained models, we chose to use the original model with 111
 270 hidden units for compression. The model is compressed by the weight clustering framework,
 271 in this case from Tensorflow [25]. We consider 25, 35, and 45 WCs in order to evaluate the
 272 trade-off between performance and complexity. The specific clustering values (25, 35, and 45)
 273 were determined through a grid search. Our goal was to identify the number of weight clusters
 274 that would provide performance comparable to the state-of-the-art work presented in [13]. This
 275 ensures a fair comparison while demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed method.

276 **4.3. Benchmarking models**

277 To benchmark the performance of our approach, we compare our NN models against several
 278 established methods (Fig. 4): CDC, ideal DBP with 20 STpS, standard DBP with 1 STpS,
 279 advanced DBP (ADBP) - subcarrier multiplexing (SCM) [5] with 1 STpS, and the NN architecture
 280 from [13].

281 The CDC method is the linear approach to compensate for chromatic dispersion by dynamically
 282 adjusting the signal with the inverse of the chromatic dispersion transfer function, based on

Fig. 4. Proposed NN models are compared against several benchmarking models.

283 the estimated chromatic dispersion after transmission. In this work, we employ both pre- and
 284 post-CDC, each compensating for 50% of the accumulated chromatic dispersion.

285 The ideal DBP with 20 STpS is included to approximate the theoretical performance by
 286 considering the entire bandwidth and reversing the Manakov equation [34]. The complexity of
 287 this method will not be benchmarked, as the ideal DBP faces implementation challenges [35],
 288 with complexity beyond what we consider.

289 The standard DBP [29] with 1 STpS is performed after demultiplexing at the subcarrier level,
 290 which means that each subcarrier is processed independently. This method approximates the
 291 inverse of the Manakov equation for each subcarrier, accounting only for SSN, but ignoring CSN.
 292 This approach reduces the computational complexity compared to full-bandwidth DBP, therefore,
 293 we consider it also as a benchmark for the complexity.

294 The ADBP-SCM, applied to DSCM systems [5], takes into account both SSN and CSN.
 295 The CSN compensation is carried out on the basis of the analytical model of time-varying
 296 cross-phase modulation (XPM) distortion proposed for wavelength division multiplexing (WDM)
 297 systems. This method adjusts the standard DBP to account for the nonlinear interactions between
 298 subcarriers, leading to improved compensation for nonlinear impairments. The ADBP-SCM
 299 considers both the CSN-induced cross-polarization modulation and phase noise. It achieves good
 300 overall performance in scenarios where the CSN significantly affects signal quality.

301 Lastly, we also consider the state-of-the-art approaches for NN-based equalizers applied to
 302 DSCM systems proposed in [13]. In this case, the authors have demonstrated the performance of
 303 the Q factor with different complexity constraints, achieving the best performance model, called
 304 “M2 iSPM+iXPM”, when training was based on perturbation coefficients. Consequently, we
 305 benchmark both the Q-factor performance and the computational complexity of our proposed NN
 306 against the M2 iSPM+iXPM models. In this work, we refer to “M2 iSPM+iXPM - 1” as their M2
 307 iSPM+iXPM model with a full complexity limit of $5 \cdot 10^5$ RMpS, whereas “M2 iSPM+iXPM - 2”
 308 corresponds to the reduced complexity model with a complexity limit of $2.5 \cdot 10^5$ RMpS.

309 5. Complexity analysis

310 This section outlines the complexity analysis for assessing the computational complexity of
 311 NN layers, both with and without weight clustering, in comparison to conventional techniques
 312 like CDC and DBP, including scenarios with and without XPM compensation. Complexity is
 313 quantified using RMpS.

314 5.1. Complexity of original NNs

315 In this work, our NN model consists of biLSTM and 1D-CNN layers. The complexity equations
 316 for this NN model are reported in detail in [9]. Starting with the biLSTM layer, we first consider
 317 the standard LSTM layer. An LSTM cell consists of three types of gates: an input gate (i_t),
 318 a forget gate (f_t), and an output gate (o_t). There is also a cell state vector (C_t) proposed as a
 319 long-term memory to aggregate relevant information throughout the time steps. The equations
 320 for the forward pass of the LSTM cell given a time step t are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 i_t &= \sigma(W^i x_t + U^i h_{t-1} + b^i), \\
 f_t &= \sigma(W^f x_t + U^f h_{t-1} + b^f), \\
 o_t &= \sigma(W^o x_t + U^o h_{t-1} + b^o), \\
 C_t &= f_t \odot C_{t-1} + i_t \odot \phi(W^c x_t + U^c h_{t-1} + b^c), \\
 h_t &= o_t \odot \phi(C_t),
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

321 where $x_t \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i}$ is the n_i -dimensional input vector at time t , $W \in \mathbb{R}^{n_h \times n_i}$ and $U \in \mathbb{R}^{n_h \times n_h}$
 322 represent the trainable weight matrices, b is the bias vector, ϕ is the “tanh” activation function, σ

323 is the sigmoid activation function, the sizes of each variable are $x_t \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i}$, $f_t, i_t, o_t \in (0, 1)^{n_h}$,
 324 $C_t \in \mathbb{R}^{n_h}$ and $h_t \in (-1, 1)^{n_h}$. The symbol \odot represents the multiplication in an element-wise
 325 (Hadamard) manner. Therefore, the number of real multiplications (RM) of an LSTM layer is:

$$\text{RM}_{\text{LSTM}} = n_s n_h (4n_i + 4n_h + 3), \quad (5)$$

326 where n_h is the number of hidden units in the LSTM cell. Similarly to RNNs, the RM can be
 327 calculated from the term associated with the input vector x_t and the term corresponding to the
 328 prior cell output h_{t-1} ; however, each term occurs four times, as we can see in Eq. (4). Therefore,
 329 we have $4n_h n_i$ and $4n_h^2$, respectively. Moreover, we also need to include the element-wise product
 330 operated three times in Eq. (4), which costs $3n_h$. Finally, the process is repeated n_s times;
 331 therefore, n_s is multiplied by the total number.

332 For the 1D-CNN layer, the equation describing this layer assuming padding equal to 0, dilation
 333 equal to 1, and stride equal to 1, can be formulated as:

$$y_i^f = \phi \left(\sum_{n=1}^{n_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_k} x_{i+j-1,n}^{in} \cdot k_{j,n}^f + b^f \right), \quad (6)$$

334 where y_i^f denotes the output or feature map, of a convolutional layer built by the filter f in the
 335 i -th input element, n_k is the kernel size, n_i is the size of the input vector, x^{in} represents the raw
 336 input data, k_j^f denotes the j -th trainable convolution kernel of the filter f and b^f is the bias of
 337 the filter f .

338 In general, when designing the CNN, parameters such as padding, dilation, and stride also
 339 affect the output size of the CNN. The output size can be computed by:

$$\text{OutputSize} = \left\lfloor \frac{n_s + 2 \text{padding} - \text{dilation}(n_k - 1) - 1}{\text{stride}} + 1 \right\rfloor, \quad (7)$$

340 where n_s is the input sequence size. In our case, with padding equal to 0, dilation equal to 1,
 341 and stride equal to 1, the output size is equal to $n_s - n_k + 1$. To calculate the complexity of a
 342 1D-CNN layer, the number of RM can be formulated as:

$$\text{RM}_{\text{CNN}} = n_f n_i n_k \cdot \text{OutputSize}, \quad (8)$$

343 where n_f is the number of filters, also known as the output dimension, n_i is the number of features
 344 in the input vector and n_k is the kernel size. As in Eq. (8), there are $n_i n_k$ multiplications per
 345 sliding window, and the number of times that the sliding window process needs to be repeated is
 346 equal to the output size. The procedure is then repeated for all n_f filters [9].

347 As a result, the complexity of our biLSTM+1DCNN layer in terms of the number of RMpS
 348 can be calculated by:

$$\text{RMpS}_{\text{NN}} = \frac{\text{RM}_{\text{LSTM}}^{\text{forward}} + \text{RM}_{\text{LSTM}}^{\text{backward}} + \text{RM}_{\text{CNN}}}{(n_s - n_k + 1) \cdot n_{\text{subcarriers}}}. \quad (9)$$

349 The total RM of the NN is divided by $(n_s - n_k + 1) \cdot n_{\text{subcarriers}}$, because the NN recovers $n_s - n_k + 1$
 350 for all subcarriers simultaneously. To be specific, the last 1D-CNN layer has $2 \times n_{\text{subcarriers}}$ filters
 351 (number 2 represents real and imaginary parts of the symbol), and each filter has the output size
 352 of $n_s - n_k + 1$.

353 5.2. Complexity of weight-clustered NNs

354 In this section, we consider the complexity of the NNs when the weight clustering technique [21],
 355 as explained in Section 3, is applied. In the biLSTM layer, for the input weight matrix W ,

356 we assume to have c_i clusters, and for the recurrent kernel weight matrix U , we assume c_h
 357 clusters. In the worst case, the number of unique real multiplications would be reduced to $n_i \times c_i$
 358 multiplications involving matrix W and $n_h \times c_h$ multiplications involving matrix U . Therefore,
 359 the number of RM for a clustered LSTM layer is:

$$\text{RM}_{\text{clustered LSTM}} = n_s (n_i c_i + n_h c_h + 3n_h), \quad (10)$$

360 For the 1D-CNN layer, we suppose that there are c_j clusters in each filter n_f . Normally, each
 361 filter has a size n_k and the input has n_i features, resulting in $n_i \times n_k$ multiplication per filter
 362 application. With weight clustering, the number of unique weights in each filter is reduced to c_j
 363 clusters. Therefore, we only need c_j multiplication per filter application. Deriving from Eq. (8),
 364 the number of RM of a cluster 1D-CNN layer reads as:

$$\text{RM}_{\text{clustered CNN}} = (n_o c_j) \cdot \text{OutputSize}. \quad (11)$$

365 Lastly, the total RMPs of the clustered model can be calculated in the same way as in Eq. (9), but
 366 with the clustered versions of these equations.

367 5.3. Complexity of CDC and DBP

368 According to Ref. [9], the computational complexity of CDC using the frequency domain
 369 equalizer (FDE) is as follows:

$$\text{RM}_{\text{CDC}} = 4 \cdot \left(\frac{N(\log_2 N + 1)q}{N - N_D + 1} \right). \quad (12)$$

370 Here, N represents the FFT size, q is the oversampling ratio, and $N_D = q\tau_D/T$ where τ_D/T is the
 371 dispersive channel impulse response, and T is the symbol interval. This complexity calculation
 372 includes two polarizations, which require four N -point FFTs and $2N$ complex multiplications. The
 373 factor of 4 accounts for the fact that one complex multiplication equals four real multiplications.
 374 The term $N - N_D + 1$ indicates the number of useful samples based on the overlap-save algorithm
 375 for blockwise FD filtering. Note that optimization of FFT size is crucial to minimize complexity.

376 For the standard DBP technique [29], DBP is performed at a subcarrier level independently.
 377 Thus, we consider the same formula as for a single carrier channel. The RM of the standard DBP
 378 is [9]:

$$\text{RM}_{\text{DBP}} = 4qN_{\text{Sp}}N_{\text{STPS}} \left(\frac{N(\log_2 N + 1)}{N - N_D q + 1} + 1 \right), \quad (13)$$

379 where N_{Sp} is the total number of spans, N_{STPS} is the number of propagation steps per span, and
 380 q is the oversampling factor. The complexity of each DBP step includes the linear part, which
 381 matches the RM of the CDC, and a nonlinear part, represented by a single RM corresponding to
 382 the multiplication with a nonlinear term.

383 For the ADBP-SCM, the RM per symbol is derived from the formula of complex multiplication
 384 per sample in Ref. [5], as follows:

$$\text{RM}_{\text{ADBP-SCM}} = 4 \cdot q \left[(M + 1) \frac{K_{\text{CD}}(\log_2 K_{\text{CD}} + 1)}{K_{\text{CD}} - P_{\text{CD}}} + M \left[6.5 + \frac{1.5K_{\text{NL}}(\log_2 K_{\text{NL}} + N_{\text{sc}} - 1)}{K_{\text{NL}} - P_{\text{NL}}} \right] \right], \quad (14)$$

385 where the multiplier 4 refers to 4 real multiplications per one complex multiplication, q is
 386 the oversampling ratio, M is the number of steps, K_{CD} is the subcarrier block size for the
 387 frequency domain CDC filter obtained by the overlap and add (OLA) method, P_{CD} is the
 388 overhead of the CDC filter for each subcarrier; $P_{\text{CD}} = (1 + \rho)\pi\beta_2(L_{\text{step}})/T_s^2$, K_{NL} denotes the
 389 OLA block size of the CSN low-pass filter, P_{NL} represents the CSN low-pass filter overhead;
 390 $P_{\text{NL}} = NL_{\text{span}} + \frac{2}{\alpha}\Delta\beta'_{\text{max}}/T_s$. Here, $\Delta\beta'_{\text{max}} = \pi(1 + \rho)\beta_2(N_{\text{sc}} - 1)/T_s$ and T_s is the sampling rate
 391 for one subcarrier. In this analysis, K_{CD} is set to 1024 and K_{NL} is set to 128.

392 **6. Results and discussion**

393 **6.1. Equalization performance**

394 We present the optical performance in terms of the Q-factor, which is calculated directly from the
 395 BER using:

$$Q = 20\log_{10}\left[\sqrt{2}\operatorname{erfc}^{-1}(2\operatorname{BER})\right]. \quad (15)$$

396 First, we compare the Q-factor of our original NNs (without WC) with analytical approaches,
 397 namely, CDC, ideal DBP 20 STpS, standard DBP [29] 1 STpS, and ADBP-SCM [5] 1 STpS,
 398 which are described in Section 4.3. Fig. 5a presents the Q-factor as a function of the optical
 399 launch power of the original NN models proposed: with 214 and 111 LSTM hidden units. The
 400 ideal DBP 20 STpS is used to provide a reference optical performance close to the ideal one.
 401 The results show that the original models with 214 and 111 hidden units provide a Q-factor
 402 improvement of 1 dB and 0.9 dB, respectively, when compared to employing CDC only. The
 403 optimal launch power also increases from 1 dBm to 2 dBm in this case. Both NN models also

(a) 40×80 km SSMF - Original NNs (without complexity reduction) compared with NN model from Ref. [13] with full complexity (M2 iSPM+iXPM-1), different approaches of DBP and CDC.

(b) 40×80 km SSMF - Reduced-complexity NNs with different numbers of weight clusters, compared to reduced-complexity NN model (M2 iSPM+iXPM-2) from [13], standard DBP and CDC.

(c) 15×80 km TWC - Original NNs (without complexity reduction) compared with different approaches of DBP and CDC.

(d) 15×80 km TWC - Reduced-complexity NNs with different numbers of weight clusters, compared with standard DBP and CDC.

Fig. 5. Q-factor as a function of the launch power for the NN-based equalizers with the original complexity (left) and the reduced complexity (right), compared to the CDC and different approaches of DBP.

404 outperform the standard DBP with 1 STpS by 0.35 dB for the model with 214 hidden units and
 405 0.24 dB for the model with 111 hidden units. As expected, the approach with higher complexity
 406 (higher number of hidden units) leads to the best optical performance. However, compared to the
 407 ADBP-SCM 1 STpS approach, the former still leads to a 1.4 dB higher Q-factor.

408 Fig. 5b shows the Q-factor as a function of the optical launch power of the original NN model
 409 proposed with 111 hidden units and compares it with the performance of its compressed versions
 410 (with weight clustering) with different numbers of WC: 25, 35, and 45 clusters. It can be observed
 411 that with a lower number of WCs, the optical performance decreases. The NN with 45 WC
 412 experienced a 0.1 dB reduction in Q-factor compared to the original NN, while the NN with
 413 35 WC showed a decrease of 0.17 dB. The NN with 35 WC demonstrated a performance close to
 414 the standard DBP 1 STpS. For the NN with 25 WC, the Q-factor was reduced to around 8.5 dB,
 415 facing a drop of 0.35 dB from the original NN. Note that all compressed models still maintain
 416 the optimum power of 2 dBm.

417 Considering the 15×80 km TWC system, Fig. 5c shows the Q-factor versus launch power for
 418 the original NNs with 214 hidden LSTM units and 111 hidden units compared with ideal DBP
 419 20 STpS, ADBP-SCM [5] 1 STpS, standard DBP with 1 STpS and CDC as baselines. The ideal
 420 DBP 20 STpS provides a reference optical performance close to the ideal one. The model with
 421 214 hidden units has a slight Q-factor improvement compared to the model with 111 hidden
 422 units, however, it comes with the cost of more complexity in terms of hidden units. Similar
 423 to the SSMF case, the performance curves of the original NN with 111 hidden units and its
 424 compressed versions in Fig. 5d exhibit a similar trend to that of the SSMF system. However, the
 425 NN-based equalizers significantly outperformed the DBP 1 STpS which only compensated for
 426 self-phase modulation. In this case, increasing the number of steps per span in the standard DBP
 427 did not further improve the Q-factor because TWC's high nonlinearity coefficient made inter-SC
 428 cross-phase modulation more significant [36]. It can be observed that even the compressed NNs
 429 can partially compensate for the CSN in the DSCM systems, showing an obvious improvement
 430 from the standard DBP. This Fig clearly reflects the trade-off between CC and performance;
 431 the higher number of WCs, the better the Q-factor. In this case, the optimal Q-factor for the
 432 original NN, and the NNs with 45 WC, 35 WC, and 25 WC were 8.36, 8.20, 8.12 and 8.01 dB,
 433 respectively.

Fig. 6. Comparison of weight distributions of all concatenated layers of (a) the original model (without weight clustering) and (b) the model with 25 weight clusters.

434 **6.2. Computational complexity**

435 This section highlights the computational complexity comparison of the proposed models and
 436 the benchmarking models.

437 First, to demonstrate how the weight distribution of the original NN models changed when the
 438 weight clustering was applied, Fig. 6a shows the weight distribution of the original uncompressed
 439 NN and Fig. 6b for the NN with 25 WC. One can observe that the unique number of weights
 440 is drastically reduced. To be more specific, there are $1.39 \cdot 10^5$ unique weights in the original
 441 model but only 125 unique weights in the NN with 25 WC. In summary, weight clustering
 442 is a powerful technique to reduce the computational complexity of NN-based equalizers in
 443 optical communications. This approach enables the NN-based equalizers to be more suitable for
 444 real-time implementation while retaining their effectiveness in mitigating fiber nonlinearity.

445 For 40×80 km of SSMF system, compared to [13], with the same transmission scenarios, our
 446 simulator provided the same optimal Q factor and the comparable Q-factor in the nonlinear regime.
 447 Ref. [13] have shown their “M2 iSPM+iXPM” models with different complexity budgets. Among
 448 these models, we consider their two most outstanding models: the model with the highest Q-factor
 449 (M2 iSPM+iXPM-1) and the model with the lowest complexity budget (M2 iSPM+iXPM-2).
 450 Their model with the highest performance with full complexity provides up to around 8.95 dB
 451 Q-factor, at the cost of $5.0 \cdot 10^5$ RMpS, while the model with the lowest complexity of $2.5 \cdot 10^4$
 452 RMpS provides a Q-factor of around 8.5 dB. Fig. 7a presents the complexity comparison of our
 453 original model with 214 hidden units and their M2 iSPM+iXPM-1 model, considering the same
 454 performance of 8.95 dB Q-factor. It can be seen that our original model with 214 hidden units
 455 requires around $1.07 \cdot 10^5$ RMpS, which is 78.6% fewer RMpS than their M2 iSPM+iXPM-2
 456 model. Similarly, Fig. 7b shows the complexity of our NN with 25 WC and their model with
 457 the lowest complexity budget (M2 iSPM+iXPM-2). It highlights that with a similar level of
 458 performance, our proposed NN with 25 WC enables a 91.1% reduction in complexity or around
 459 2215 RMpS.

460 Fig. 8 illustrates the complexity reduction of the compressed model compared to the original
 461 model with 111 hidden units. The compressed model with 25 WC provided a 97.9% reduction
 462 from the original model, at the cost of 0.45 dB Q-factor drop.

463 Next, it is crucial to evaluate the trade-off between performance and complexity in weight
 464 clustering for NN. In this regard, Fig. 9a illustrates the complexity in terms of RMpS as a function

(a) Our original NN with 214 hidden units compared to the full-complexity NN model (M2 iSPM+iXPM-1) from Ref. [13], with the same Q-factor of 8.95 dB.

(b) Reduced-complexity NN with 25 WC, compared to reduced-complexity NN model (M2 iSPM+iXPM-2) from Ref. [13], with the same Q-factor of 8.5 dB.

Fig. 7. Complexity in RMpS comparison of our models and the models M2 iSPM+iXPM in Ref. [13], for 40×80 km of SSMF.

Fig. 8. Complexity in RMpS comparison of our original model with 111 hidden units and its compressed version with 25 WC for 40×80 km of SSMF.

of the number of WC, using CDC (FDE) and standard DBP 1 STpS as benchmarks for 40×80 km of SSMF system. The NN with 35 WC achieved performance levels comparable to standard DBP 1 STpS, but with a 31.5% reduction in complexity (RMpS). However, when comparing the complexity of the NN equalizer to that of CDC, it becomes clear that significant improvements are necessary to achieve lower complexity levels, particularly in terms of multiplicative operations. Notably, while CDC typically requires around 150 multiplications per recovered symbol, the compressed NN still requires between 2000 and 3000 multipliers in its lower complexity configurations. For the standard DBP 1 STpS, more than 4200 RMpS are typically necessary.

Similarly, for 15×80 km of TWC system, Fig. 9b illustrates the trade-off between performance and complexity for the NNs with varying numbers of WCs, using the standard DBP with 1 STpS and CDC as benchmarks. As expected, a higher number of WCs results in a higher Q-factor. However, the improvement of the Q-factor is not linearly increased with the number of WC, indicating that beyond a certain threshold, additional WCs contribute marginally to performance enhancement. To achieve comparable performance to the standard DBP at 1 STpS, the model required 10 WCs, resulting in a 34% reduction in RMpS. Note that the standard DBP with more steps per span did not improve the performance due to its limitation in compensating for the CSN.

Fig. 9. Comparison of complexity (RMpS) between biLSTM+CNN and traditional channel equalizers (DBP 1 STpS and CDC) as a function of the number of clusters utilized in weight clustered compression.

481 In this study, we observed that aggressive weight clustering (reducing the number of clusters
482 to very low values) is less effective for DSCM systems than for simpler single-carrier, single-
483 channel systems. For instance, Ref. [21] demonstrated that as few as three weight clusters could
484 achieve performance comparable to DBP in single-carrier systems. However, for the more
485 complex DSCM system, at least 25 clusters were needed for SSMF transmission and 10 clusters
486 for TWC transmission to achieve similar performance to standard DBP with 1 STpS. These
487 findings highlight the increased computational and modeling demands of DSCM systems, where
488 the balance between performance and complexity becomes particularly critical. The ongoing
489 challenge of optimizing NN equalizers to reduce computational complexity, especially in terms of
490 multiplication operations, while maintaining high performance, needs to be further investigated.

491 To show the comprehensive result compared to the previous literature, Table 1 summarizes
492 different equalization approaches for the 40×80 km SSMF systems, including CDC, ideal DBP,
493 standard DBP, ADBP-SCM, the models from previous literature [13], and our NN models with
494 different complexity limits. The table shows their Q-factor performance, optimum launch power,
495 and computational complexity in terms of RMpS.

496 Our current approach is to recover only one polarization at a time. Although technically
497 feasible to modify the output of the model to simultaneously recover the X and Y polarizations,
498 this approach was not explored in this study. For consistency, the CDC block and the NN
499 equalizer were applied independently to each polarization channel. It is worth noting that during
500 the inference phase, the computational complexity in terms of RMpS would not increase if
501 two separate models were deployed for the two polarizations. This is because the total number
502 of recovered symbols would also double, maintaining the RMpS at the same level. Moreover,
503 modifying a single model to recover both polarizations could potentially reduce RMpS, as a
504 shared architecture could leverage additional efficiencies while increasing the number of symbols
505 recovered per inference.

Name	Method	Average Optimal Q-factor (dB)	Optimum Launch Power (dBm)	Complexity (RMpS)
CDC	Linear	7.90	1.0	146
Standard DBP 1 STpS	Nonlinear	8.60	1.5	4256
ADBP - SCM 1 STpS [5]	Nonlinear	10.37	3.5	$1.07 \cdot 10^5$
NN Eq. - M2 iSPM+iXPM-1 [13]	Nonlinear	8.95	2.0	$5.0 \cdot 10^5$
NN Eq. - M2 iSPM+iXPM-2 [13]	Nonlinear	8.41	1.5	$2.5 \cdot 10^4$
Our original NN Eq.(214 hidden units)	Nonlinear	8.95	2.0	$1.07 \cdot 10^5$
Our original NN Eq. (111 hidden units)	Nonlinear	8.84	2.0	$3.1 \cdot 10^4$
Our NN Eq. with 45WC	Nonlinear	8.74	2.0	3611
Our NN Eq. with 35WC	Nonlinear	8.67	2.0	2913
Our NN Eq.with 25WC (Proposed)	Nonlinear	8.49	2.0	2215

Table 1. Summary of the different equalization approaches, with their Q-factor performance, optimum launch power and complexity in terms of RMpS for 40×80 km of SSMF.

506 7. Conclusion

507 This article has proposed the low-complexity NN-based equalizers for DSCM systems based
508 on weight clustering. We presented a detailed benchmarking analysis of various methods for

509 nonlinearity compensation in DSCM systems, with a focus on comparing the performance of
510 a proposed NN-based equalizer and its computational complexity. We compared our models
511 with traditional approaches such as CDC, standard DBP, ADBP-SCM, and NN models based
512 on the perturbation analysis proposed in [13]. Our study reveals that the NN-based equalizer,
513 particularly when enhanced with weight clustering techniques, can achieve comparable Q-factor
514 performance with a significantly reduced computational complexity. Specifically, the proposed
515 NN-based models demonstrated up to a 91.1% reduction in complexity compared to the previous
516 literature and 31.5% compared to the DBP, while providing a similar Q-factor improvement.
517 These findings suggest that NN-based equalizers, with their ability to balance performance and
518 computational efficiency, could play a crucial role in advancing the capabilities of next-generation
519 optical networks.

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525 **Data Availability.** Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this
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527 References

- 528 1. R.-J. Essiambre, G. Kramer, P. J. Winzer, *et al.*, "Capacity limits of optical fiber networks," *J. Light. technology* **28**,
529 662–701 (2010).
- 530 2. T. Xu, N. A. Shevchenko, Y. Zhang, *et al.*, "Information rates in kerr nonlinearity limited optical fiber communication
531 systems," *Opt. Express* **29**, 17428–17439 (2021).
- 532 3. J. C. Cartledge, F. P. Guiomar, F. R. Kschischang, *et al.*, "Digital signal processing for fiber nonlinearities," *Opt.*
533 *express* **25**, 1916–1936 (2017).
- 534 4. E. F. Mateo, F. Yaman, and G. Li, "Efficient compensation of inter-channel nonlinear effects via digital backward
535 propagation in wdm optical transmission," *Opt. Express* **18**, 15144–15154 (2010).
- 536 5. F. Zhang, Q. Zhuge, M. Qiu, *et al.*, "Xpm model-based digital backpropagation for subcarrier-multiplexing systems,"
537 *J. Light. Technol.* **33**, 5140–5150 (2015).
- 538 6. X. Liang and S. Kumar, "Multi-stage perturbation theory for compensating intra-channel nonlinear impairments in
539 fiber-optic links," *Opt. express* **22**, 29733–29745 (2014).
- 540 7. A. Amari, O. A. Dobre, R. Venkatesan, *et al.*, "A survey on fiber nonlinearity compensation for 400 gb/s and beyond
541 optical communication systems," *IEEE Commun. Surv. & Tutorials* **19**, 3097–3113 (2017).
- 542 8. M. Ibnkahla, "Applications of neural networks to digital communications—a survey," *Signal processing* **80**, 1185–1215
543 (2000).
- 544 9. P. Freire, S. Srivallapanondh, B. Spinnler, *et al.*, "Computational complexity optimization of neural network-based
545 equalizers in digital signal processing: a comprehensive approach," *J. Light. Technol.* (2024).
- 546 10. P. J. Freire, Y. Osadchuk, B. Spinnler, *et al.*, "Performance versus complexity study of neural network equalizers in
547 coherent optical systems," *J. Light. Technol.* **39**, 6085–6096 (2021).
- 548 11. S. Deligiannidis, A. Bogris, C. Mesaritakis, and Y. Kopsinis, "Compensation of fiber nonlinearities in digital coherent
549 systems leveraging long short-term memory neural networks," *J. Light. Technol.* **38**, 5991–5999 (2020).
- 550 12. S. Srivallapanondh, P. J. Freire, A. Alam, *et al.*, "Multi-task learning to enhance generalizability of neural network
551 equalizers in coherent optical systems," in *49th European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC 2023)*, vol.
552 2023 (IET, 2023), pp. 640–643.
- 553 13. A. Bakhshali, H. Najafi, B. B. Hamgini, and Z. Zhang, "Neural network architectures for optical channel nonlinear
554 compensation in digital subcarrier multiplexing systems," *Opt. Express* **31**, 26418–26434 (2023).
- 555 14. W. S. Saif, S. K. O. Soman, and O. A. Dobre, "Deep learning-assisted nonlinearity compensation in subcarrier-
556 multiplexing coherent optical systems," *J. Light. Technol.* (2024).
- 557 15. H. Sun, M. Torbatian, M. Karimi, *et al.*, "800g dsp ASIC design using probabilistic shaping and digital sub-carrier
558 multiplexing," *J. lightwave technology* **38**, 4744–4756 (2020).
- 559 16. M. Qiu, Q. Zhuge, M. Chagnon, *et al.*, "Digital subcarrier multiplexing for fiber nonlinearity mitigation in coherent
560 optical communication systems," *Opt. Express* **22**, 18770–18777 (2014).
- 561 17. P. Poggiolini, A. Nespola, Y. Jiang, *et al.*, "Analytical and experimental results on system maximum reach increase
562 through symbol rate optimization," *J. Light. Technol.* **34**, 1872–1885 (2016).
- 563 18. D. Welch, A. Napoli, J. Bäck, *et al.*, "Digital subcarrier multiplexing: Enabling software-configurable optical
564 networks," *J. lightwave technology* **41**, 1175–1191 (2023).

- 565 19. D. Welch, A. Napoli, J. Bäck, *et al.*, “Point-to-multipoint optical networks using coherent digital subcarriers,” *J.*
566 *Light. Technol.* **39**, 5232–5247 (2021).
- 567 20. Y. Zhang, M. O’Sullivan, and R. Hui, “Digital subcarrier multiplexing for flexible spectral allocation in optical
568 transport network,” *Opt. Express* **19**, 21880–21889 (2011).
- 569 21. P. J. Freire, A. Napoli, B. Spinnler, *et al.*, “Reducing computational complexity of neural networks in optical channel
570 equalization: From concepts to implementation,” *J. Light. Technol.* **41**, 4557–4581 (2023).
- 571 22. S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, “Long short-term memory,” *Neural computation* **9**, 1735–1780 (1997).
- 572 23. F. A. Gers, J. Schmidhuber, and F. Cummins, “Learning to forget: Continual prediction with lstm,” *Neural computation*
573 **12**, 2451–2471 (2000).
- 574 24. S. Han, H. Mao, and W. J. Dally, “Deep compression: Compressing deep neural networks with pruning, trained
575 quantization and huffman coding,” arXiv preprint arXiv:1510.00149 (2015).
- 576 25. T. M. O. Team, “Clustering algorithm in tensorflow model optimization,” [https://github.com/
577 tensorflow/model-optimization/blob/v0.7.2/tensorflow_model_optimization/
578 python/core/clustering/keras/clustering_algorithm.py#L24-L194](https://github.com/tensorflow/model-optimization/blob/v0.7.2/tensorflow_model_optimization/python/core/clustering/keras/clustering_algorithm.py#L24-L194) (2023). Accessed:
579 2024-08-21.
- 580 26. D. Marcuse, C. Manyuk, and P. K. A. Wai, “Application of the manakov-pmd equation to studies of signal propagation
581 in optical fibers with randomly varying birefringence,” *J. Light. Technol.* **15**, 1735–1746 (1997).
- 582 27. G. P. Agrawal, “Nonlinear fiber optics,” in *Nonlinear Science at the Dawn of the 21st Century*, (Springer, 2000), pp.
583 195–211.
- 584 28. S. Musetti, P. Serena, and A. Bononi, “On the accuracy of split-step fourier simulations for wideband nonlinear
585 optical communications,” *J. Light. Technol.* **36**, 5669–5677 (2018).
- 586 29. E. Ip and J. M. Kahn, “Compensation of dispersion and nonlinear impairments using digital backpropagation,” *J.*
587 *Light. Technol.* **26**, 3416–3425 (2008).
- 588 30. S. J. Savory, “Digital coherent optical receivers: Algorithms and subsystems,” *IEEE J. selected topics quantum*
589 *electronics* **16**, 1164–1179 (2010).
- 590 31. X. Zhou, “An improved feed-forward carrier recovery algorithm for coherent receivers with m -qam modulation
591 format,” *IEEE Photonics Technol. Lett.* **22**, 1051–1053 (2010).
- 592 32. M. Qiu, Q. Zhuge, M. Chagnon, *et al.*, “Laser phase noise effects and joint carrier phase recovery in coherent optical
593 transmissions with digital subcarrier multiplexing,” *IEEE Photonics J.* **9**, 1–13 (2017).
- 594 33. P. J. Freire, D. Abode, J. E. Prilepsky, *et al.*, “Transfer learning for neural networks-based equalizers in coherent
595 optical systems,” *J. Light. Technol.* **39**, 6733–6745 (2021).
- 596 34. G. P. Agrawal, *Fiber-Optic Communication Systems* (Wiley, 2021), 5th ed.
- 597 35. X. Li, X. Chen, G. Goldfarb, *et al.*, “Electronic post-compensation of wdm transmission impairments using coherent
598 detection and digital signal processing,” *Opt. express* **16**, 880–888 (2008).
- 599 36. A. Napoli, D. Rafique, B. Spinnler, *et al.*, “Performance dependence of single-carrier digital back-propagation on fiber
600 types and data rates,” in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference*, (Optica Publishing Group, 2014), pp. W2A–49.